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5th International Tourism Week (ITW) Conference Partner

AN EMPIRICAL RESEARCH ON THE EFFECT OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON DESTINATION CHOICE

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Abstract

Social media is one of the factors that plays a significant role in rapid and active share of information which influence travelers destination choices. Recent studies in the literature suggest that the social media is one of the most important factors that affect travel intentions and travel planning processes. However, there has been relatively little substantive research focusing on the relationship between social media and destination choice. In this context, the aim of the study is to explain the relationship between social media and destination choice. The research framework developed in this study is tested by 125 academic staff serving at ten different tourism vocational schools and tourism faculties in Turkey. Research findings reveal that there are significant relationship between the two dimensions of the social media and destination choice. Accordingly, social media affects the destination choice positively.

Keywords: social media, destination choice, tourism, eWom

1. Introduction

"At the close of the 20th century, roughly between 1997 and 2000, a set of hardware and software technologies collectively known as the Internet had an enormous diffusion and radically changed most of our economic and social life. In the last few years, a further "revolution" has impacted the way we communicate, work and conduct business". The buzzword for this is Web 2.0 and social media. (Milano et al., 2011: 1). Social media and Web 2.0 are two popular buzzwords as well as technological concepts, which have brought about pervasive changes in business-to-business communication, business to-customer communication, and customer-to-customer communication (Leung et al., 2013:3). Web 2.0 is no longer just a static page, but a dynamic platform which allows users the autonomous generation of content and the possibility of telling their own experiences (Miguens et al., 2008: 1). In other words, the key characteristic of Web 2.0 is that it enhances collaboration and sharing of information online and is built around social media software which makes it possible for people to communicate and form communities using their computers (Munar, 2012: 101-102).

Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) define social media as "group of Internet-based applications that are built on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0, and that allow the creation and exchange of User Generated Content" (Fotis et al., 2012: 14). Social media is the media that is published, created and shared by individuals on the internet, such as blogs, images, video and more as well as online tools and platforms that allow internet users to collaborate on content, share insights and experiences, and connect for business or pleasure (Chung and Austria, 2010: 581). Social media represents a variety of forms such as social networks (e.g., Facebook), photo sharing sites (e.g., Flickr, Instagram), video creating and sharing sites (e.g., YouTube), online communities, microblogging tools (e.g., twitter), social tagging (e.g., Digg), newsreaders (Google Reader), public Internet boards and forums, review/rating websites (e.g., TripAdvisor), and individual websites (Kang and Schuett, 2013: 93). On the other hand, social media have transformed the worldwide web into a more social and participatory phase in which users co-create, collaborate, share and modify content.

The importance of social media has been studied widely in the context of influencing travel planning, destination choice and intention to purchase (Sreenivasan et al., 2012: 21) In literature, there are some studies that shows social media provide information about the activities of destinations which users interested in and influence their travel intentions or travel planning processes (Cox et al., 2009: 761; Parra-López et al., 2011: 651; Sigala, 2010: 437; Xiang and Gretzel, 2010: 186; 437; Hsiao, 2012: 176; Fotis et al., 2012: 22; Leung et al., 2013: 18; Ayeh et al., 2013: 140). Currently, much of the researches emphasis has focused on the relationship social media and travel intentions or travel planning process, but little (Hays et al., 2012; Jalilvand and Samiei, 2012; Munar, 2012) has explored the effects of social media on destination branding, destination management and destination choice. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of the social media on destination choice.

2. Literature review

Travel and tourism has been one the most popular subjects in the worldwide web. This is because tourism products can hardly be evaluated prior to their consumption and thus the functionality of the entire industry depends on the intangible and digital character of the distribution of tourism products and on accurate and reliable information. One of the most important information sources for travel planning is word of mouth (Vrana and Zafiroopoulos, 2010: 595-596). Specifically, social media has become a powerful

source of "word of mouth" communication. Since social media provides sites for consumers to share their experiences and opinions with others, it can have a positive or negative influence on consumers. In addition, social media influences the purchase decision making process and travel planning also is a major sources of online travel information (Lim et al., 2012: 197-198; Kwok and Yu, 2013: 85).

Social media websites, representing various forms of consumer-generated content (CGC) such as blogs, virtual communities, wikis, social networks, collaborative tagging, and media files shared on sites have gained substantial popularity in online travelers' use of the Internet. Many of these social media websites assist consumers in posting and sharing their travel-related comments, opinions, and personal experiences which then serve as information for others (Xiang and Gretzel, 2010: 179; Ayeh et al., 2013: 132). In other words, social media empowers individual travelers, they can portray, reconstruct, and relive their tourism experience through the online channel (Ip et al., 2012: 419). There are five types of social media tools which are using generally; social networking websites (Facebook, LinkedIn), blogs and micro-blogs (Blog-

ger, Twitter, Travel Blog), content community sites (Youtube, Flickr, Instagram, Myspace), collaborative projects (Wikipedia, Wikitravel), consumer review & rating websites (Trip Advisor, Epinions). These social media tools provide as a source of information travellers before trip, impact their destination and accommodation choices during trip, also these provides travellers to compare and share experiences after the trip (Fotis et al., 2012: 14-15; Sotiriadis and Zyl, 2013: 106).

Social media exist in a variety of forms and serve numerous benefits in vacation trips. In this context the perceived benefits of using social media for planning vacation trips is functional, social and psychological and hedonic (Parra-Lopez et al., 2011; Senders et al., 2013: 43)

- *Functional benefits:* use of social media when organizing and taking vacation trips to obtain information. In other words, it includes elements related to information gathering, which helps in decision-making processes.
- *Social benefits:* it refers to communication with other members, the construction of relationships, the exchange of ideas and opinions, and the visitors' involvement in the exchange of information when organizing and taking vacation trips.
- *Psychological benefits:* these are linked to individuals' trust in social media, to belonging to communities and, consequently, to finally being a member of them. Psychological benefits being initially necessary when a tourist joins an environment of social media technologies for organizing and taking his/her tourist trip.
- *Hedonic benefits:* when organizing or taking tip, one must also take into account experiential aspects like enjoyment and entertainment. These aspects are covered in the hedonic benefits category.

Social media are new agents developing and managing tourism information. Specially, it provides destination related information and knowledge (Munar, 2012: 102). In other words, social media provides information about products and services, and serves as a recommendation about destinations. On the other hand it reduces uncertainty and plays an important role in increasing tourists' travel intentions, creating a favorable image of the destinations (Jalilvand and Samiei, 2012:592-604). By way of social media, travellers receive first-hand authentic travel experiences and many travelers tend to use and trust these informations for searching for travel information, selecting travel suppliers and destinations (Vrana and Zafiroopoulos, 2010: 596). Consequently, consumers might have already shared their experiences in a travel review website or within their social media networks, thus social media plays an active role in destination choice (Kwok and Yu, 2013: 84).

In the choice of destination, there are three phases (pre-experience, experience during travel and post-experience) that are influential in travel formation process. Pre-experience built on other people's travel stories, before travelling, experience during travel or stay, today increasingly shared real-time through mobile applications, post-experience, which disseminates comments, evaluations, emotions (Milano et al., 2011: 4). Tourists generally have scarce knowledge about the attributes of a destination which they have not visited yet. Therefore, the image and attitude dimensions of a place as a tourism destination are likely to be important elements in the destination choice process (Um and Crompton, 1990: 433). Besides; according to Hill's (2000) Destination Choice Set Model, the two sets of factors have impact upon destination changing

or destination funneling process and the final choice. Firstly, environmental factors that mean external forces like information source, culture, family, lifestyle and destination features are the factors which influence the destination choice decisions. Secondly, individual trait factors which refer to personal characteristics such as personal motivation, personality, past experiences also affect the choice process (Mutinda and Mayaka, 2012: 1593).

In this study, it will be examined external factors which are identified social interaction and research that affect the choice of destination. Today, social media is the most widely accepted tools for social interaction and research. In this context, the purpose of this study investigates the affect of the social media upon the destination choice. Therefore in order to test the relationship between the dimensions of the social media and the destination choice hypothesis shown below is developed.

H1: There is a statistically significant relationship between receiving information through social media and the choice of destination.

H2: There is a statistically significant relationship between sharing information through social media and the choice of destination.

3. Research methodology

3.1. Objective, method and scope

The aim of the study is to explain the relationship between social media and destination choice. Survey technique is used to collect data. The research results are limited to the area of application of the questionnaire in ten tourism vocational schools and faculties' staffs because of costs and opportunities.

3.2. Sampling

The sample group of the study is composed of academic staff, studying in the field of tourism in ten different schools in Turkey which are determined through convenient sampling method. Therefore out of 150 questionnaires that have been sent, 130 (%86) have returned and 125 (%83) of them are accepted as valid and are included in the evaluations.

3.3. Measuring instrument

Measures used in the questionnaire are exclusively designed for the purpose of this study inspired by the studies from literature (Cox et al., 2009; Lopez et al., 2011; Kastner ve Stangl, 2011; İşlek, 2012; Bayram, 2012; Aymankuy et al, 2013). Pilot study where (n=50) was applied after the creation of measurement. As a result of the conducted pilot study, it's observed that the items in the factor analysis, displayed a proper distribution. In measurement, usage of social media was measured with 21 items, destination choice was measured 16 items and there are also 7 demographic questions in the questionnaire. For answers to the statements of survey, a Likert-type metric, that is, expressions with five intervals has been used. Anchored such; «1-strongly disagree, 2- disagree, 3- agree or not agree, 4- agree, 5-strongly agree».

3.4. Statistical methods

Obtained from the study, the data are evaluated using SPSS for Windows 15.0 program. Factor analysis is used with the variables related to social media and destination choice and the structural validity of the social media and destination choice dimensions are tested. To determine the reliability levels of the scales, Cronbach Alpha values are computed. Multiple regression analysis is used to explain the relationship between the dimensions of the social media and the choice of destination.

4. Research findings

4.1. Demographic findings

64% of academic staffs, who have participated in the research, are male, and 36% are female. Approximately 29% of academic staffs are under age of twenty nine. 45.5% of the academic staffs remaining are between the ages of 30 and 39; and 20.3% them are between the ages of 40 and 49, and 6% them are in the group of 50 years and older. 30% of academic staffs are single, 62% are married and 8% are in other group. 29% of academic staffs are lecturer, 10% are instructor, 32% are research assistant, 21.5% are assistant professor, 6% are associate professor and 2.5% are professor.

7.3% of academic staffs, who have-participated in the research use internet in a week 0-5 hours, 13% of academic staffs use 6-10 hours, 12.2 % of academic staffs use 11-15 hours, 16.3% of academic staffs use 16-20 hours, 14.6% of them use 21-25 hours, 10 % of them use 26-30 hours and 26% of them are in the group of 31 and above. 50.4% of academic staffs, who have participated in the research use social media in a week 0-5 hours, 20.3% of academic staffs use 6-10 hours, 15.4% of academic staffs use 11-15 hours, use 5.7% of academic staffs use 16-20 hours, 3.3% of them use 21-25 hours, 2.4% of them use 26-30 hours and 2.4% of them are in the group of 31 and above.

4.2. Descriptive statistics

Distribution of social sharing sites used by academic staffs participated in the research are; 91.2% facebook, 84% youtube, 38.4% twitter, 8.8% foursquare, 21% LinkedIn, 7% Myspace, 7% Blogger and 9% others (google +, academia, flickr, Xing). When arithmetic means of answers given to survey statements by academic staff who participated in the study are analyzed in table 1.

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Facebook	114	2,00	5,00	4,0351	,99494
Youtube	105	2,00	5,00	3,7238	1,02371
Twitter	49	1,00	5,00	3,1020	1,04572
Foursquare	12	1,00	4,00	2,8333	,93744
Linkedin	27	1,00	5,00	2,8148	,96225
Myspace	12	1,00	5,00	2,5000	1,24316
Blogger	8	1,00	5,00	3,0000	1,30931

4.3. Factor and reliability analysis

In the study, the structural validity and reliability levels of measures were tested. First, data of the variables related to social media were put into factor analysis and the varimax rotation was obtained. In the principal component analysis, the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test result (KMO value ,899) and the result of Bartlett test (1172.107; $p < 0.01$) were significant. As a result of the varimax rotation of the data related to social media variables, removing the items with factor loadings under 0.40 from the analysis, two factor solutions has been obtained. Emerged factors, explain 62.540% of the total variance. The findings on the resultant factors, factor loadings, explained variances, and internal consistency coefficients calculated for each factor (measure) are summarized in Table 2.

Table 2: Rotated Factor Loadings with Calculated Social Media Measures

Factor 1: Receiving Information Through Social Media(explained variance=32.359%; Cronbach's Alpha= 0.89)	
1. Social media tools help to contact people having same holiday pleasure with me	0.777
2. Social media tools help to follow sharings about the destination of people having same pleasure with me	0.760
3. Following activities that others organize about tourism destinations through my social media account	0.738
4. Using the social media tools to follow tourism campaigns	0.727
5. Exchange information through the social media with people who have already travelled	0.676
6. Following the contents shared about destination on my social media account	0.631
7. Being a member of groups that organized for tourism destinations on my social media account	0.544
8. Having information about tourism sites and activities through to the social media tools	0.466
Factor 2: Sharing Information Through Social Media(explained variance = 30.181% ; Cronbach's Alpha = 0.88)	
9. Sharing photos and videos related with my holiday experience on my social media account	0.874
10. Comment about my holiday experience on my social media account	0.815
11. Sharing photos and videos about tourism destination on my social media account	0.678
12. Comment to contents shared about tourism destination on my social media account	0.664
13. Writing something about tourism destination on my social media account	0.636
14. Trust on sharings that comment about holiday experience and suggest through the social media	0.501

Extraction method: Principal component analysis - Rotation method: Varimax rotation

After applying factor analysis to the data of destination choice variables, for the principal

component analysis, the result of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin test (KMO value, 0.911) and the Bartlett test result (1474.256; $p < 0.01$) were found significant. Two factors solution has been achieved as a result of varimax rotated factor analysis. Resultant factors, explain 68.793% of the total variance. The findings on the resultant factors, factor loadings, explained variances, and internal consistency coefficients calculated for each factor are summarized in Table 3.

Table 3: Rotated Factor Loadings with Calculated Destination Choice Measures

Factor 1: Social Interaction of the Destination Choice (explained variance = 44.655%; Cronbach's Alpha = 0.94)

1. Following travellers' comments about destinations on the social media	0.860
2. Following photos and videos shared about destinations on the social media	0.841
3. Following information about the destinations on the social media	0.812
4. Affected by photos and videos shared about destinations on the social media	0.787
5. Affected by travellers' comments about destinations on the social media	0.753
6. Sharing photos and videos related destination where I took holiday on my social media account	0.719
7. Affected by information presented about destinations on the social media	0.703
8. Inform people about current progress on tourism on my social media account	0.688
9. The information that I have reached through the social media affect my holiday destination	0.669
10. Taking holiday in any destination where I haven't thought before by affecting sharings	0.608

Factor 2: Research of the Destination Choice (explained variance = 24.138% ; Cronbach's Alpha = 0.82)

11. While planning holiday, searching destinations on the social media is affordable	0.872
12. While planning holiday, searching destinations on the social media takes little time	0.838
13. While selecting destination, I initially search on the social media	0.592
14. While planning holiday, I search on the social media tools	0.532

Extraction method: Principal component analysis - Rotation method: Varimax rotation

4.4. Findings on the research hypotheses

According to correlation analysis findings, receiving information through social media ($r=0.716$, $p < 0.01$) and sharing information through social media ($r=0.693$, $p < 0.01$) dimensions have a significant relation with the destination choice. Correlation analysis findings support hypothesis H1 and H2. There is a positive relationship between the dimension of social media and destination choice.

Table 4: The Correlation Between The Dimension of Social Media and Destination Choice

	1	2	3	Mean
Receive Information Through Social Media	1			3.10
Share Information Through Social Media	,794**	1		2.98
Destination choice	,716**	,693**	1	3.25

** $p < 0.01$

According to the regression analysis finding, R^2 determination coefficient value, (Table 5); 55% of variance in destination choice is explained by receiving information through social media and sharing information through social media which are two dimensions of social media. The regression model, explaining the impact of the social media on destination choice, is valid (with $F=75,973$; $p < 0.001$). The positive beta value shows that the increase in independent variable leads to an increase in destination choice, or a decrease in independent variables results in a decrease in destination choice. Accordingly; it can be said that social media affect the destination choice positively.

Table 5: Effects of Social Media Upon Destination Choice

	R ²	F	β	p
Social Media	,555	75,973		0.000
Receive Information Through Social Media			,450	0.000
Share Information Through Social Media			,335	0.001

5. Conclusion

Social media is one of the most widely used communication instruments in the 21st century described as the age of the Internet and technology. Besides being used as a communication tool, social media is also effective agent in many areas of people's lives. In other words, social media is one of the factors that plays a significant role in individuals' purchasing decisions, hotels and restaurants choice, holiday planning processes and in all other choices regarding their social lives. Especially today, the fact that individuals share their photos, videos and comments through social media has either positive or negative impact on their purchasing processes. In this context, social media is expected to impact directly or indirectly individuals' purchase decisions in many sectors.

Today, social media, which is used as a tool for individuals who are in need of socialization, is considered to be highly effective on the tourism industry. Because tourism is an industry in which interaction and knowledge are widely used among people. In this respect, tourists access information related to travel through social media easier and faster and they benefit from this information. Therefore, it is possible that social media can be effective at all stages of travel planning processes. In other words, individuals, who obtain information through social media or who share the information they have, can benefit from this information in processes such as means of transportation, accommodation and destination selection.

The objective of this study is to investigate the effect social media on destination choice. From the research findings, it is seen that participants of the research use social media effectively. The majority of respondents share items such as pictures, video and content related to tourism destinations they are interested in more on facebook. When the findings of the research are analyzed, other social networking sites which participants often use are Youtube, Twitter, Foursquare, LinkedIn, MySpace and Blogger. Besides, findings of the correlation analysis suggest that there is a positive and significant relationship between social media and the choice of destination. Research findings also suggest that "receiving information through social media" and "sharing information through social media" queries appear to be effective dimensions on destination choice. In this context, H1 and H2 hypotheses have been adopted. In addition. In regression analysis, on the other hand, 55% of the variability in destination choice is described by social media. Research findings cover participants included in the study.

This paper is expected to contribute to literature, as there are limited available studies investigating the relationship between social media and the destination. Timeliness of the research topic will make possible to establish new relationships with variables by expanding research scope. It is believed that conducting studies which examine the impact of social media on accommodation selection or carrying out new studies examining the role of social media in processes before, during and after the holidays will contribute to the literature.

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